

Ring-opening reaction of aziridines using aqueous polyacrylamide (PAM) as the reaction medium

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Abstract : A novel efficient method for the hydrolysis of aziridines using aqueous polyacrylamide (PAM) is described. An aqueous PAM solution serves as the reagent, the catalyst and the reaction medium. The reaction is fast (30 min), operationally simple, regioselective for a wide range of substrates and produces ring-opening products in high yields. This method provides a promising alternative to existing procedures.

Keywords : Aziridines, hydrolysis, ring opening, PAM.

Introduction

Aziridines are versatile building blocks for the synthesis of nitrogen-containing molecules¹⁻³. These reactive small-ring heterocycles can be readily ring-opened with nucleophiles to furnish valuable 1,2-difunctionalized fine chemicals⁴⁻⁶. Recently, ring-opening reactions of aziridines have been used to prepare biologically active compounds for drug research and development^{7,8}. However, most of these reactions suffer from the fact that a Lewis acid or a protonic acid is necessary for the reaction to proceed⁹. There are few reports of reactions under neutral conditions, and these reactions which are performed in organic solvents produce poor regioselectivity.

In 2007, Das and co-workers^{10,11} reported a catalyst-free highly regio- and stereoselective ring-opening reaction for epoxides and aziridines. The reactions used sodium azide polyethylene glycol (PEG) as the reaction medium and were completed in 30-45 min at room temperature with products having yields of 95-99%. The hydrolysis of the aziridines is believed to be promoted by the PEG. The activity of the substrates is increased by hydrogen bonding with the PEG, so the reaction can be performed under mild conditions.

Polyacrylamide (PAM) is a water-soluble polymer made from monomers of acrylamide. The amphiphilic copolymers are widely used in a variety of industrial ap-

plications such as the treatment of sewage, the clarification of industrial waste water, solid/liquid separations, strength additives for papermaking, flocculation, drainage and retention aids, corrosion inhibitors, enhanced oil recovery, drilling fluids, and coatings¹²⁻¹⁵. In addition, PAM is a biologically compatible polymer, which is inexpensive and environmental friendly. Like PEG, PAM should be capable of forming multiple hydrogen bonds and supplying H⁺ to produce the acidic conditions needed for the hydrolysis of aziridines. Herein, a new method that uses aqueous PAM as the reaction medium to facilitate the ring-opening of *N*-tosyl aziridines is reported.

Results and discussion

Eight *N*-tosyl-activated aziridine substrates were reacted in a PAM aqueous solution under reflux to produce the corresponding β -amino alcohol. The results are shown in Table 1. All the reactions were completed within 30 min, and the yields were greater than 91%.

Regioselectivity of the opening reactions is specific. For each substrate, the water molecules only attack a specific carbon atom to generate the adjacent amino alcohol. When compared with a pure water system¹⁶ (no PAM), the reaction time was shortened from 6-10 h to 0.5 h. The reaction processing is extremely simple because the product is obtained simply by extraction and washing. The need for a column chromatography purification step is eliminated. The use of a PAM aqueous

Table 1 Hydrolysis of aziridines using aqueous PAM

Entry	Aziridine	Product	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1		0.5	93	
2		0.5	92	
3		0.5	94	
4		0.5	92	
5		0.5	95	
6		0.5	94	
7		0.5	91	
8		0.5	92	

Ts = Tosyl

solution for the ring-opening of *N*-tosyl-activated aziridines is a very good reaction system

In general aziridines are insoluble in aqueous solutions. The presence of PAM solubilizes the aziridines and plays an important role in the ring-opening of the *N*-tosyl-activated aziridines. The promoter action of the PAM is primarily due to its flexible long chains which provide multiple weak hydrogen bonds with the substrate. These interactions allow the water molecules to more easily approach the aziridines and stabilize the intermediate formed between the water molecules and the substrate which makes it easier to carry out the ring-opening reactions of the aziridines. A proposed reaction mechanism for the hydrolysis of aziridines in aqueous PAM solution is shown in Fig. 1, using 2-phenyl-1-tosylaziridine as an example. Two H₂O molecules interact with one substrate in the reaction system. First, an intermolecular hydrogen bond is formed between a H₂O molecule and the O atom of the sulfonyl. This weakens the C-2-N bond. Then, another H₂O molecule attacks the C-2, and the intermediate is stabilized by conjugation of the C-2 with the benzene ring.

At the same time, the flexible molecular chains of the PAM form multiple hydrogen bonds with the substrate. These serve as secondary bonds and also stabilize the intermediate to make the reaction proceed smooth. Ring opening reactions of alkyl substituted aziridines can also be explained by this mechanism. For example hydrolysis of 2,2,3-trimethyl-1-tosylaziridine also produces the product of C-2 ring-opening. Because the C-2 is connected to two -CH₃ groups, the electron donating group (-CH₃) makes this intermediate more stable.

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of aziridines using an aqueous PAM solution

Experimental

All aziridines were prepared in our laboratory according to the literature¹⁷. The other reagents were purchased commercially and used without further purification. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on AVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer and the chemical shifts were referenced to CHCl₃ (δ 7.27) in CDCl₃. IR spectra were measured using the AVATAR 360 infrared spectrophotometer.

Preparation and analysis of PAM solution :

A PAM solution was prepared by the reaction of acrylamide with distilled water according to a standard procedure¹⁸. The PAM was tested by gel permeation chromatography, and the results are as follows : Mn (Dalton) : 23000; Mw (Dalton) : 193305; MP : 176121; Mz (Dalton) : 409698; Mz + 1Z + 1 (Dalton) : 566448; Mv (Dalton) : 193305; polydispersity : 8.404718. The degree of hydrolysis (HD%) of the PAM was determined by titration with a 0.10 N HCl standard solution¹⁹. The HD% was 2.0.

General procedure for the ring-opening reaction of aziridines with an aqueous solution of PAM :

A mixture of aziridine (2 mmol) and PAM solution (10 mL) was added to a round bottom flask and refluxed for 0.5 h. After completion of the reaction, as monitored by TLC, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, and water (10 mL) was added. The product was extracted with ethyl acetate (15 mL \times 3), and the combined organic layers washed with H₂O and then with a saturated aqueous solution of NaCl. After, drying with anhydrous MgSO₄, the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. Pure product was obtained by recrystallization with petroleum ether and ethyl acetate. Eight different aziridines were used as substrates in the experiments.

Spectroscopic data :

N-(2-Hydroxy-2-phenylethyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²⁰, white solid; yield 93% ; m.p. 104–106 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3401, 3149, 1918, 1662, 1598, 1318, 1148, 1098, 1088, 1065; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.69 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.23–7.25 (7H, m), 5.68 (1H, s), 4.76 (1H, dd, *J* 2.4, 8.4 Hz), 3.48 (1H, brs), 3.14–3.17 (1H, m), 2.94–3.00 (1H, m), 2.37 (3H, s).

N-(2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²¹, white solid; yield 94%; m.p. 91–

93 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3477, 3281, 2924, 2854, 1326, 1159, 814, 706; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.17–7.72 (8H, m), 4.81 (1H, ddd), 3.25 (1H, ddd), 3.02 (3H, ddd), 2.39 (3H, s).

N-(2-Hydroxy-2-*p*-tolylethyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²⁰, oily liquid; yield 92%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3502, 3277, 2926, 2870, 1323, 1159, 711, 706; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.92–7.82 (8H, m), 4.75 (1H, ddd), 3.26 (1H, ddd), 3.05 (1H, ddd), 2.42 (3H, s), 2.27 (3H, s).

N-(2-Hydroxy-2-phenylpropyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²⁰, oily liquid; yield 92%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3360, 3262, 2925, 2855, 1306, 1160, 764, 702; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.40–7.82 (9H, m), 3.24 (1H, ddd), 3.13 (1H, ddd), 2.43 (3H, s), 1.55 (2H, s).

N-(2-Hydroxycyclopentyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²⁰, white solid; yield 95%; m.p. 87–89 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.79 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.28 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 5.99 (1H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 4.02–4.04 (1H, m), 3.60 (1H, brs), 3.24–3.28 (1H, m), 2.39 (3H, s), 1.86–1.93 (1H, m), 1.75–1.81 (1H, m), 1.44–1.56 (3H, m), 1.33–1.37 (1H, m).

N-(2-Hydroxycyclohexyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²⁰, white solid; yield 94%; m.p. 124–127 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.30 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 5.32 (1H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 3.28–3.33 (1H, m), 2.81–2.92 (2H, m), 2.42 (3H, s), 1.98–2.00 (1H, m), 1.50–1.73 (3H, m), 1.05–1.30 (4H, m).

N-(2-Hydroxycycloheptyl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²², oily liquid; yield 91% ; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3452, 3141, 1599, 1498; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 1.15–1.87 (10H, m), 2.43 (3H, s), 2.61–2.70 (1H, m), 2.95–3.07 (1H, m), 3.44–3.52 (1H, m), 5.00 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.33 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.9 Hz).

N-(3-Hydroxy-3-methylbutan-2-yl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide²³, white solid; yield 92%; m.p. 128–129 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3498, 3279, 2980, 2856, 1331, 1157, 668, 540; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.75 (2H, d), 7.30 (2H, d), 4.67 (1H, d), 3.18 (1H, dq), 2.39 (3H, s), 1.85 (1H, s), 1.17 (3H, s), 1.15 (3H, s), 0.93 (3H, d).

In conclusion, an efficient method for the hydrolysis of aziridines using an aqueous solution of PAM has been developed. The PAM aqueous solution serves as the reagent, the catalyst and the reaction medium. The method offers significant advantages such as operational simpli-

city, very fast reaction time (0.5 h), high isolated product yields, general applicability to a wide variety of substrates, and excellent regioselectivity. Thus it provided a better and more practical alternative to existing procedures.

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